

EFFECT OF NEEM EXCEL ON THE BIOLOGY OF *PAPILIO DEMOLEUS* L. LEPIDOPTERA : PAPILIONOIDEAE

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ABSTRACT : *Papilio demoleus* is a common and wide spread swallow tail butterfly which is also known as lime butterfly. The butterfly is a pest and invasive species found from Asia to Australia. The caterpillars can completely defoliate young Citrus trees and also delicate citrus nurseries. Azadirachtin, the active ingredient of neem has been demonstrated to have an antecedent and insect growth regulatory effects, negative influence on the reproduction of female as well as reduction in oviposition and infertility of eggs. Neem excel 0.15% EC was tested on citrus leaves and treated on 4th and 5th instars of caterpillar of *P. demoleus*. Mortality was found highly significant at 0.1% level of significance. However other concentrations also revealed significant mortality percentage at 5% level of significance. Adult emergence was considerably affected by 0.04% concentration, which caused 64.44% emergence in comparison to 95.00% in control. Pre oviposition and oviposition periods were significantly delayed while post oviposition period was shortened to 93.33 hrs at 0.04% concentrations. Fertility was found reduced and after hatching percentage of malformed individuals were increased.

Key words : *Neem excel, Biology, Papilio demoleus.*

INTRODUCTION

The neem tree, *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. is the most promising plant species using as an insecticides. Its various parts like, leaf, root, bark and seeds have been used but seeds are the main source of bioactive compounds for neem based insecticide formulations (Copping and Duke,2007). Among the most important benefits of neem application are the insecticidal and repellent characteristics of the products (Hussein,2000). It has antifeedant and insect growth regulatory effects, negatively influence the reproduction of female as well as reduction in oviposition rate and infertility of eggs (Kaur *et al.*,2001). Azadirachtin based insecticides ensures a selective activity against target insects and a minimum persistence in field and safe to predators and friend insects like spiders and coccinellids (Mann and Dhaliwal,2001).

Neem affects many different physiological activities in insects, including regulation of growth, reproduction, diapause and behaviour. It has a hormonal effects, affecting both ecdysteroid and Juvenile hormone titers (Gracia *et al.*,2006 and Abdullah & Subramaniam,2008). Azadirachtin also interferes with Chemoreception and exerts direct deterrent effects on many insect tissues such as muscles, foot, body and gut epithelial cells (Mordue,2004 and Capinera & Froeba,2007).

However, the effects of neem application are not always consistent, being somewhat dependent upon the insect species, time of application, method of application and concentration applied (Koul,1991). The effectiveness of neem extracts also varies and can be influenced by origin of the neem tree, method of extraction, temperature, and humidity (Ermel *et al.*,1987).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The adults and caterpillars of *Papilio demoleus* were reared in cage and Jars with the foliage of citrus plants in pot. For the adult food solution, tap water (2 parts) and honey syrup (1 part) soaked in to cotton were given. After mating female butterfly laid egg on lower part of tender leaf and shoot once caterpillars have hatched from eggs they reared in jar with fresh leaf. The newly hatched caterpillar stays in the middle of the upper side of the leaf. The first, instar caterpillar is black with a black head and two rows of the fleshy spine. II, III and IV instar has white marking on 8th and 9th segment which resemble a white patch of uric acid deposited in a birds droppings, helping them escape predation. V instar caterpillar is green with patches. For the study 4th and 5th instar caterpillar were isolated and 10 larvae were selected and were offered citrus leaf treated with different concentrations of neem excel (Containing 0.5% EC azadirachtin) viz. 0.02%, 0.03% and 0.04%.

Experiment were conducted in three replication to avoid discrepancy. Neem treated leaf removed after 24 hrs and then fresh leaves offered throughout the study. The mortality was found throughout duration of 4th and 5th instars. A control treatment was also run for each replicate. Treated survivors from each concentration were maintained to study their longevity and adult emergence. Emerged adults were Sexed and each pair was kept in cage. Pre mating, Pre oviposition, oviposition and post oviposition period were determined. The eggs were observed on pot plant and then an average egg laid by a single female was calculated to obtain fecundity and hatched and unhatched eggs was ascertained to get fertility. Longevity of treated survivors were compared with control.

Table. 1 Effect of neem excel on biology of *Papilio demoleus*.

Conc. (%)	Caterpillars mortality (%)			Caterpillar longevity (hr)		Adult emergence (%)	Pre mating (hr)	Ovi position (hr)	Post ovi position (hr)
	4 th instar	5 th instar	Total	4 th instar	5 th instar				
0.02	10.00 t=1.59	18.43 t=1.86**	18.43	139.66 t=2.49*	216.66 t=1.65*	82.66 t=1.65*	89.33 t=1.90**	76.00 t=1.8*	184.76 t=3.65*
0.03	13.66 t=2.94	10.00 t=2.94	23.66	142.16 t=2.28*	224.852.25* t=2.25*	77.66 t=2.49	75.00 t=1.67	88.33 t=2.36*	135.40 t=4.85*
0.04	21.66 t=1.95	15.00 t=2.25	36.66	145.88 t=2.33	228.50 t=2.33**	64.44 t=284*	86.33 t=2.84	99.00 t=2.51*	93.33 t=6.123
Control	3.33	4.88	16.56	16.56	186.50	95.00	58.56	66.31	250.66

*-Significant at 5% level of significance. **-Significant at 0.01% level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Date of the Table.1 revealed that mortality of 4th instar was increased with increase concentration of neem. In 4th instar caterpillar highest mortality was found 21.6% with 0.04% concentration. It was followed by 13.66% and 10.00% with use of 0.03% and 0.02% of neem excel, respectively. Mortality also occurred in 5th instar but found to be less in comparison to 4th instar. Kaur *et al.* (2001) reported effect of hexane extract of neem seed Kernel on development and reproductive behaviour of *Spodoptera litura*. Longevity of survivor of both instar was significantly delayed with the increase of concentrations of neem in the food (Table.1). Smith and Mitchel (1988) also obtained azadirachtin inhibit the activity of 20 monoorggenase, which was responsible to convert ecdysone to its activity metabolite, 20 hydroryecdysone (Shah *et al.*, 2005).

Adult emergence percentage were reduced with treated food. It was found 82.66%, 77.66% and 64.44% with the use of 0.02%, 0.03% and 0.04% concentration of neem formulations. It was found highly significant with all concentrations. Suppression of adult emergence was also found by Banukiran & Panwar (2002), Man *et al.* (2001) and Abdullah & Subramaniam (2008). Studied feeding response of *Epilachna indica* towards neem products.

Pre mating pre oviposition, oviposition and post oviposition period were considerably reduced in adults produced by 4th instars which taken neem treated leaves. Fakhri & Ansari (2005) and Adel & Zaki (2010) also found reduction in Diaphorina mortality of eggs up to 96% was reported by Khan & Khan (2001) and Khosravi & Sendi (2013).

The fecundity was decreased with increase of concentration of neem in food. Eggs did not hatched properly. Fertility was also revealed decreasing trend. The neem might indirectly reduce the female reproductive rate (Khan and Khan 2001). Malformation in caterpillar and adults of F₁ generation obtained from treated 4th instar of variable degree in whole body, wings and legs. A number of emerged adults were found having folded, twisted and deformed wings as well as shrunken abdomen. This results showed close conformity with the findings of Fakhri & Ansari (2006), Capinera & Froeba (2007) and Mohamed *et al.* (2017). Where neem derivatives had shown great potential in retardation of growth and development of insects.

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